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Milestone 12: First feedback on the identified common software quality metrics and measurement tools from the science clusters

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Survey on the software quality metrics

During the July 2025 WP4 meeting on 2025-06-04, the WP4 leads administered a questionnaire via the [Mentimeter platform](#) to the attendants of the meetings responsible for the EVERSE pilots. The goal of the questionnaire was to gain feedback on the quality metrics, considering the upcoming review of the Reference Framework, and determine if the current document accurately reflects the views of the different science clusters. The feedback was incorporated in the second version of the Reference Framework, that can be found at [1].

While the initial collection of tools and services was available in [2], a curated list tailored to the science clusters was not yet available for distribution and testing to the pilots, so it was agreed with the WP2 leads and TF2.1 leads to postpone this part of the review to a later stage (with potential hands-on demonstrations) so that this feedback could be more effective.

1. Structure of the survey

The survey asked the following questions to the participating pilot representatives:

- How does your cluster prioritise the quality metrics, in terms of Reference Framework categories?
- Where do quality dimensions make a difference? (With an optional request for examples)
- What software quality checklists are relevant to your cluster?

We also added two questions relevant to the RSQKit in terms of roles, whose feedback has been discussed with RSQKit editors. The questionnaire was followed by a brief discussion in the meeting.

2. Results of the survey

The quality metrics chosen by EVERSE are representative of those used in the clusters. The top 5 software quality metrics in order of priority for the clusters are:

ESCAPE

Performance efficiency

Reliability

Maintainability

Functional suitability

Flexibility

Specifically, performance efficiency and reliability are crucial in resource-constrained situations, such as an experiment's trigger system that must make data-retention decisions in milliseconds. Maintainability, functional suitability and flexibility are key factor of code reuse, which is often common practice for multiple developers and users in large scientific collaborations.

PANOSC

Functional suitability

Performance efficiency

Flexibility

Maintainability

Reliability

ENVRI

Interaction capability

Flexibility

Reliability

Performance efficiency

Functional suitability

LIFE RI

Flexibility

Functional suitability

Reliability

Maintainability

Performance efficiency

The quality dimensions are seen as crucial for the sustainability, usability, and trustworthiness of research software, with modular and well-documented software (e.g., [Bioconductor](#) packages) cited as examples.

SSHOC

Compatibility

Functional suitability

Reliability

Performance efficiency

Security

The SSHOC pilot responsible cited compatibility as one of most important aspects as it is important that tools work with multiple existing systems and types of data. Reliable tools are most likely to be used multiple times, and performance is important for users to decide what resources to use (local vs HPC) and how to plan experiments.

The pilot representatives from ESCAPE, LIFE RI and SSHOC also suggested a list of quality checklists that will be / have been investigated in the context of WP4.

3. Next steps

This questionnaire represented a first step towards the EVERSE pilots' adoption of the common software quality metrics. As evidenced by the replies, different clusters prioritise different metrics but there is broad agreement on the usefulness of the list that has been compiled to date. The next step to focus the feedback on the tools as well is to create targeted shorter lists of tools to be tried (and

respective documentation) that start from measuring and improving the quality metrics prioritised by each cluster. This will be compiled by WP4 in collaboration with WP2 and WP3 for distribution to the pilots.

Bibliography

[1] Chue Hong, N., Diblen, F., Garijo, D., Maassen, J., Peru, G., Orfanou, A., Pechlivanis, N., Psomopoulos, F., Amodeo, S., Bos, P., Doglioni, C., Nenadic, A., Sparks, M., & Sufi, S. (2025). EVERSE Reference Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15856368>

[2] Huste, T., Linnemann, K., Vuillaume, T., Gamgami, A., Bajare, S., Juckeland, G., Bartolini, M., Clarke, A., Garijo, D., Pechlivanis, N., Psomopoulos, F. D3.1 – First collection of existing tools and services usable in the Science clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness. Report.